

Research Article

Protection of Human Rights of Tribal Communities in Visakhapatnam Agency: Challenges and Limitations

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Abstract

India is home to the world's second-largest concentration of tribal populations, primarily situated in forests and hilly regions. Human rights, which are the inherent entitlements of every individual, constitute a vital element of the global socio-cultural fabric. These rights are embodied in abstract principles and values, protected by laws, constitutions, and international agreements. Historically, there were numerous human rights violations and brutalities, particularly against tribal women. Isolation and social discrimination were common experiences for these tribal communities, who were consistently oppressed by mainstream society. Unfortunately, these tribal people were often stigmatized by mainstream Indian society, enduring social exclusion and even violence. In this connection this paper draws out the realities in analytical way protection of human rights of tribal communities in Visakhapatnam agency.

Keywords: Indigenous communities, Tribal societies, Human rights, Colonial intervention, Social exclusion, Stigmatization, Scheduled Tribes, Right to Health, PESA Act, Forest Rights Act, Right to Information, Socio-economic development, Tribal autonomy

Introduction

The Indigenous communities in India boast a rich history that predates the colonial government's arrival. These tribal societies, existing prior to colonial intervention, held their own rights and responsibilities within their self-governing framework. India is home to the world's second-largest concentration of tribal populations, primarily situated in forests and hilly regions. Unfortunately, these tribal people were often stigmatized by mainstream Indian society, enduring social exclusion and even violence.

Human rights, which are the inherent entitlements of every individual, constitute a vital element of the global socio-cultural fabric. These rights are embodied in abstract principles and values, protected by laws, constitutions, and international agreements. In addition to encounters with various civilizations, tribal communities also faced influences from foreign missionaries in the past and, more recently, from dominant society forces with fundamentalist tendencies.

Historically, there were numerous human rights violations and brutalities, particularly against tribal women. Isolation and social discrimination were common experiences for these tribal communities, who were consistently oppressed by mainstream society. The movement for tribal rights and equal status in Indian society was initially championed by Mahatma Gandhi.

Article 342 of the Indian Constitution defines Scheduled Tribes as those tribes or tribal communities officially recognized by the President through public notification. Article 14 of the Constitution guarantees equality before the law and equal protection of the laws for all individuals within Indian territory. Given the social disadvantages faced by these tribal populations, the Indian Constitution provides them with several rights to safeguard their interests.

These communities contend with various social issues, including untouchability and high illiteracy rates. Article 17 of the Indian Constitution explicitly abolishes untouchability in any form. After gaining independence in 1947, the Indian government enacted several policies and established a ministry to protect tribal rights. The Constitution also confers special rights upon Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes.

Furthermore, it is widely recognized by different groups and women's organizations that the limited representation of women in democratic political institutions is responsible for the lack of gender sensitivity in government policies and programs. Ensuring gender equality in tribal regions is just as crucial as strengthening land rights for women, redefining 'family' to encompass female-headed households, or ensuring joint ownership of property for both spouses during new allotments, in terms of women's fundamental and human rights. Tribal women, who belong to marginalized and deprived groups within tribal communities, are particularly affected by developmental processes and often marginalized in policy decisions.

Therefore, there is a pressing need to establish a nationwide movement founded on tribal socio-cultural traditions, human rights, and a women's perspective. The primary objective of this paper is to examine the safeguarding of human rights for tribal people in the Agency Area of Visakhapatnam District in Andhra Pradesh

Methodology

The present study aimed at studying about the 'Protection of the Human Rights of Tribal people in Visakhapatnam Agency area: Issues and Constraints'. The present study is based on both the primary and secondary data collected through field survey with structured interview schedule. Secondary data was collected from Census Reports, ITDA and Chief Planning Office records of the Visakhapatnam district.

The Primary Data was collected from 300 Sample respondents by adopting Multi Stage Random Sampling Method. 11 mandals in Visakhapatnam Agency were divided into 3 regions and from each region one mandal namely Paderu mandal, Chintapalli mandal and Munchingput mandal was selected for the study. Three villages from each mandal i.e. Sangodi, Dummuputtu and Ainodu villages from Paderu mandal, similarly Pasulabanda, Domalagondi and Lingalagudi villages from Chintapalli mandal and Ramulu, Taddapalli, Sariyaputtu villages from Munchingput mandal i.e. a total of 9 villages were selected for the study of agency area of Visakhapatnam district of Andhra Pradesh by using Pre-designed Interview Schedule.

Right to Education

Education for all is not a mere question of literacy. It is an empowerment of people. Education is the path that leads to that world. Education is the fundamental right of every human being, the means for self-realization and self-expression, physical, intellectual, social, emotional and spiritual development of human beings. Education has to be free and compulsory at least in the elementary and fundamental stages. The constitution of India, states that the state shall

endeavour to provide within a period of 10 years (Art.45) from the commencement of this constitution for the free and compulsory education of all children until they complete the age of 14 years.

A review of the fifth plan identified several states which were not in a position to allocate the necessary economic resources to achieve the goal of universal elementary education; there were socially disadvantaged groups like economically poor, scheduled castes, scheduled tribes whose children existed at the periphery of the schooling system; there were socio-economic compulsions in families that forced parents not to send the children to schools, and that the irrelevant nature of curricula and lack of essential facilities were responsible for the slow progress in the area. Education is the only way out by which the tribal people can be made aware of their rights otherwise they would be of no use, so the main focus of the Government should be to provide them education.

Table -1

Percentage Distribution of Sample respondents by Literacy Level

S.No	Educational Status	No.of respondents	Percentage
1	Illiterate	121	40.33%
2	Primary	93	31.00%
3	Secondary	39	13.00%
4	Intermediate	29	9.67%
5	Graduate	18	6.00%
	Total	300	100

Source: Field Data

The above table-1 shows the distribution of respondents of Paderu, Chintapalli and Munchingput madals by literacy level. The respondents with respect to literacy level are divided into 5 categories such as illiterate, primary, secondary, intermediate and graduates. It is inferred from the above data that more than 40% of the respondents are illiterates and 31% of them have completed primary education. Around 13% of the respondents have completed secondary education, 9.66% of the respondents have completed intermediate and only 6% of the respondents have completed graduation. There will be some respondents in primary and secondary level of education who have stopped their education in between i.e. drop outs.

Right to Health

The development of health is not a fragmented process, it is integral in its nature which includes the overall growth and development of different socio-cultural, economic, educational, political and environmental factors. Health and sanitation is becoming a huge problem for tribal people because of illiteracy and ignorance and they are not ready to welcome the modern concepts of health and sanitation. Tribal people have another problem that they still believe in superstitions and super natural powers and believe that diseases are caused by these super natural powers. Alcoholism is one of the major problems existing in tribal regions. The lack of knowledge and proper sanitation has made the tribes vulnerable to these diseases. Moreover the dearth of medical facilities and the reluctance of the doctors to work in rural areas have aggravated the situation.

These diseases take a heavy toll on tribal life. Suspicion of tribal people and lack of faith in modern doctors have made them not to avail themselves of the modern medical facilities. So the problem of Health and Sanitation is a very serious issue and steps should be taken by the Government in tribal regions for spreading awareness on healthy environment in tribal areas.

Table-2

Distribution of Sample respondents by Source of Treatment

S.No	Source of Treatment	No.of respondents	Percentage
1	Self-treatment	115	38.33%
2	Doctor	135	45%
3	Traditional Treatment	50	16.67%
	Total	300	100

Source: Field Data

The Table-2 clearly shows that variation in source of treatment before and after implementation of Human Development Programmes in tribal areas. In present scenario the respondents who were used to self and traditional treatments reduced to 55% and 45% of the total respondents started visiting doctors which is drastic and positive change was found in the survey area.

Forest Right Act

The National Forest Policy of 1988 recognizes symbiotic relationship between forest and Tribal communities yet; the Tribal people have been systematically victimized under the Forest Act of 1927. In 2006, the government of India brought the Scheduled Tribes and Other Traditional Forest Dwellers (Recognition of Forest Rights) Act. The Act is aimed at undoing the age-old injustice done to Tribal communities by restoring and recognizing their pre-existing rights. The recognition and restoration has been, however passing through rough weather in respect of its implementation. The Government of India till today has failed to notify the Rules of Procedures of the Forest Rights Act of 2006.

Violation of PESA Act in India

To reinforce the constitutional provisions for protection of the Tribal communities, this important Panchayat (Extension to the Scheduled Areas) PESA Act 1996, has been enacted in recent years. The act empowers the scheduled tribes to safeguard and preserve the traditions and customs of the people, their cultural identity, community resources and customary mode of dispute resolution through the Gram Saba. The Panchayat (Extension to Scheduled Areas) 1996 Act does provide for women's presence in Panchayats in the 6th Scheduled Areas, but the issues involved are diverse and complex. Interestingly, the provisions of the Panchayat Act hardly find its due place in latter and spirit. PESA Act is a law enacted by the Government of India to enable the Gram Sabhas of the tribal regions to self governs and protect their natural resources. However, there is also a need to extend the provisions of the 1996 Act to the other states with tribal concentrations like Andhra Pradesh, Chhattisgarh, Gujarat, Himachal Pradesh, Jharkhand, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Odisha and Rajasthan and not to other Scheduled Areas including those in Manipur.

The act gave the power to the Gram Sabhas to commend the programmes, plans and projects made for the development of the tribal people and they should be consulted before making any acquisition of land in Scheduled Tribe areas for the development programmes. Overall this act

provided the people the right to preserve their land and natural resources and recommendation of the Gram Sabha at appropriate levels for any developmental programme in the tribal area.

Table-3

Percentage Distribution of Sample respondents by Awareness on Human Rights

S.No	Awareness	No.of respondents	Percentage
1	Right to Health	64	21.33%
2	Right to Education	104	34.67%
3	Social Development	63	21.00%
4	Legal Rights	33	11.00%
5	Political Rights	28	9.33%
6	No Awareness	08	2.67%
	Total	300	100

Source: Field Data

Table-3 provides the data on awareness of human development parameters among the tribes in the surveyed mandals. Now at present 97% of the total respondents are aware of the various forms of human rights and only 3% of them were unaware. Majority (34.67%) of the respondents were found to be having awareness on Right to Education followed by Right to Health (21.33%), Social Development (21%), Political Rights (9.33%) while 2.67% were found to be in category of No Awareness about Human rights.

Right to Information

A democratic polity represents an obligation on the part of the state to govern on behalf of its citizens. The obligation also includes the duty to keep the citizenry informed of the nature and basis of objectives, policies, plans and decision-making undertaken by the state. The converse of this duty obligated on the state is the right of citizens to obtain information on all matters that directly or indirectly concern public interest. The constitution of India in its Art.19 (1) (a) guarantees to all citizens the Right to Freedom of speech and expression. Over the years, this fundamental right has been dynamically interpreted to constitute the obverse of the Tight to know, such that one cannot be exercised without the other.

Tribal Problems in India

In India, the tribes are socially and economically very backward compared to the rest of the nation's population. The tribal areas have remained under- developed, neglected, and even alienated from the rest of the land for centuries. The tribals are living under precarious economic conditions due to continuous neglect of the rulers and the successive governments over a long period and a lack of appreciation of their special problems, inadequate investment and non integration of the tribal economy. Owing to the lack of transport, communication and other facilities, they have been cut off from the main stream, till recently they were virtually enslaved and kept as bonded labors by money lenders from whom they had borrowed money at fantastic rates of interest and failed to repay. Tribal economy is relatively backward, under developed and open and exploited. The impact of development programmes on it and the tribal's capacity to absorb them are limited. Tribal lands have been acquired by the Government for various development purposes contractors, moneylenders, missionaries etc., have also acquired the land of the tribals for their own benefits.

Since independence Indian government is putting strenuous efforts to bring the tribals in to mainstream of the economy and to improve their socio-economic conditions. Government has made massive efforts for the socio-economic development of tribal people through organized economic planning. The planners somehow missed to cognizance of these different states of economy of tribals causing practical difficulties in implementation. The social and economic levels of the tribal communities are not homogenous. But they are at different levels of variability tribal development cannot be uniform of the tribals in each region and sometimes each community.

Constitutional Rights for the Welfare of the Tribal People

The Constitution of India has provided special provisions to the tribal people to safeguard their interests.

1. Article 15 of the Indian Constitution states that the state shall not discriminate any citizen on grounds of religion, race, caste, sex, place of birth or any of them. This explains that every citizen of India is provided equal rights and opportunities without any discrimination.
2. Government of India has made reservation for the tribes in employment under Article 16(4) of the Constitution of India.
3. The Government of India has reserved seats in The House of People (Lok Sabha) and The State Legislative Assemblies under Article 330 and 332 of The Constitution of India.
4. Article 19(5) of the Constitution of India guarantees the tribal people right to own property and enjoy it in any part of the country.
5. Article 338 of The Constitution of India grants the right to appoint a Commissioner to look after welfare activities of tribes.
6. Article 46 of the Constitution of India states that, The State shall promote with special care the educational and economic interests of the weaker sections of the people and in particular, the Scheduled Castes and the Scheduled Tribes, and shall protect them from social injustice and all forms of exploitation.
7. Under Article 275(i) of the Constitution of India the Centre Government is required to give grants-in-aid to the State Government for approved Tribal Welfare Schemes.

Development Policies for Tribal Communities

Tribal people who constituted 8.6% of the total population of India as per 2011 census also constituted 55.1% of the total development project-induced displaced persons up to 2010 on account of mega developmental projects like industries, mining, dams, wild life sanctuaries, parks and conservation of nature, etc. Development projects have become more problematic particularly in Andhra Pradesh during the last few decades. It is the duty of Government to take care of their interests and ensure them equal rights in the society. In India not only the Central Government, State Government or authorities are helping the tribes to ensure their rights but other voluntary organizations. The government of India should adopt "Indigenous and Tribal Peoples Intellectual Property Rights Act" to provide for a system of community intellectual rights protection of indigenous and tribal peoples with respect to the development of genetic resources and the conservation of the country.

Findings

- ☐ Majority of the respondents (40.33%) were found to be illiterate while 6% respondents were found to be graduate and above graduate.
- ☐ Majority of the respondents (45%) were found to be visiting doctors for health treatment while 16.67% of the respondents go for traditional treatment.

- ② Majority (34.67%) of the respondents were found to be aware of Right to Education followed by Right to Health (21.33), Social Development (21%), Legal rights (11%), Political Rights (9.33%) while 2.67% of the respondents were not having awareness on any of the aspects related to human rights.

Suggestions

- ② There is need to adopt holistic approach for attaining Human Development among the tribals through creation of Education, Health, Agriculture, Infrastructural facilities.
- ② Special focus should be given a creation of awareness about developmental programmes and take concrete steps to avail the developmental programmes by every family by way of transparency in functioning.
- ② Need to implement the reservations to tribals at all levels with true spirit and to create congenial atmosphere to exercise their vote freely.
- ② There is a need to create awareness to all legal rights for the tribal people.

Conclusion

The Central and State Governments have indeed shown significant interest and made efforts toward the advancement of tribal communities, but the progress achieved thus far remains only moderately satisfactory. The government's inability to effectively implement these policies can be attributed to a lack of political will, deficiencies in administrative machinery, procedural delays, and inadequate monitoring. Presently, tribal individuals often struggle to assert their rights due to a lackluster response from authorities.

Education plays a pivotal role in achieving development, and as such, the government should prioritize steps in this direction. A nation's progress is contingent upon the education and awareness of its citizens. It is the government's responsibility to safeguard the interests of tribal communities and ensure their equal rights within society. In India, not only the Central and State Governments but also various voluntary organizations are actively contributing to securing the rights of tribal communities.

The challenges and issues faced by tribal communities should not be ignored or isolated from the broader development agenda of the government. The Sixth Five-Year Plan acknowledged that, despite three decades of development efforts, socially, economically, and educationally disadvantaged sections have not experienced the desired improvements. It is our belief that the government and all political parties must collaborate in earnest for the welfare of tribal communities, refraining from diplomatic postures on this critical matter. Consequently, there is an urgent need to establish tribal autonomy to protect the human rights of tribal people.

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